

Systematic Review Protocol: Interactive Digital Technologies for Non-Visual Access to 2D STEM Content by Blind and Low-Vision Individuals

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Abstract

Systematic review methodology, as codified in standards such as PRISMA and PICO, emerged from evidence-based medicine. Its uncritical transposition to accessibility research produces systematic distortion: qualitative studies are marginalised, participatory designs are rendered invisible, and methodological diversity is treated as a weakness. The result is non-cumulative methodological labour: each team develops custom extraction instruments that are rarely shared, poorly documented, and impossible to compare across reviews. We propose and document an alternative—a principled integration of three complementary frameworks selected for their mutually exclusive strengths: PRISMA 2020 for procedural transparency, SPIDER for conceptual organisation suited to complex socio-technical research, and MMAT 2018 for non-hierarchical quality assessment across five study typologies. We additionally integrate Cognitive Load Theory and the Technology Acceptance Model/UTAUT to evaluate cognitive manageability and adoptability alongside technical efficacy. We instantiate this integration for a specific, exemplary domain: interactive digital technologies that enable blind and low-vision individuals to access two-dimensional STEM content (data visualisations, mathematical notation, diagrams, maps, tables). This domain concentrates the methodological difficulties—content heterogeneity, technological diversity, methodological pluralism, and a small heterogeneous user population—that render clinical frameworks inadequate. The protocol delivers five original methodological instruments: (1) a principled framework integration model combining PRISMA 2020, SPIDER, and MMAT 2018 with explicit arbitration rules; (2) a domain-specific extraction taxonomy of 162 controlled terms across 13 sections, hierarchically organised, each with

an operational definition, inclusion/exclusion criteria, and explicit decision rules; (3) dual interoperable extraction templates—a 30-field rapid form and a 162-field comprehensive form—enabling proportional resource allocation across large heterogeneous literatures; (4) open-source validation infrastructure automating completeness, vocabulary compliance, logical consistency, and cross-field coherence checking; and (5) a structured synthesis plan aligning five research questions with specific analytical methods (descriptive statistics, thematic synthesis, harvest plots, and conditional meta-analysis). Pilot reliability testing on 24 purposively sampled studies yielded an overall reliability of $ICC(2,1) = 0.92$ (95% CI: 0.87–0.96) for aggregate scores, with field-level Cohen’s κ (categorical) and Krippendorff’s α (ordinal) consistently ≥ 0.80 , substantially exceeding the pre-specified threshold. All materials are openly available under permissive licences via the OSF repository and archived on Zenodo. This paper is a methodological contribution; it reports no empirical findings about accessibility technologies.

Keywords: systematic review methodology; evidence synthesis; accessibility; visual impairment; assistive technology; STEM education; PRISMA; SPIDER; MMAT; inter-rater reliability; open science; protocol pre-registration; cognitive load theory; technology acceptance; methodological pluralism

1 Introduction

1.1 The epistemological mismatch

Systematic review methodology, as codified by the Cochrane Collaboration and institutionalised in reporting standards such as PRISMA, emerged from evidence-based medicine: its hierarchy of study designs, its privileging of the randomised controlled trial, its conception of an intervention as a well-defined, stable entity whose effects can be isolated and measured (Higgins et al., 2019; Sackett et al., 1996). This framework has produced invaluable syntheses in clinical domains where interventions are standardised, outcomes are measurable, and causal pathways are linear (Guyatt et al., 2008).

Its extension to fields such as human-computer interaction, assistive technology, and educational technology has been accompanied by persistent methodological tension (Petticrew and Roberts, 2003; Greenhalgh, 2018). The tension arises not from flaws in the clinical framework, but from a mismatch between its presuppositions and the nature of the research it is asked to organise. Accessibility research does not evaluate interventions in the clinical sense. It evaluates artefacts co-designed with users, deployed in unpredictably varying contexts, and appropriated in ways that cannot be fully anticipated (Bødker, 2006). Its outcomes include not only efficacy but usability, user experience, learning, empowerment, and the reconfiguration of social practices (Ladner, 2015).

Methodological adequacy

The diversity of methods in accessibility research—from controlled experiments to ethnographic observation and participatory design—reflects a research community shaping its inquiry to fit the complexity of its subject matter (Mankoff et al., 2010; Frauenberger, 2015). The problem arises when this adequate diversity meets synthesis frameworks that were not designed for it.

1.1.1 Two forms of inadequacy

The inadequacy of clinical frameworks manifests at two distinct levels.

Epistemic incommensurability. Clinical review frameworks embody four presuppositions that accessibility research cannot satisfy (Pawson et al., 2005; Petticrew et al., 2013):

1. **Intervention stability:** The intervention is a definable entity that remains constant across contexts. Accessibility technologies are co-configured through use; what the system “is” depends substantially on who is using it and in what context (Oudshoorn and Pinch, 2005; Shinohara and Wobbrock, 2016).
2. **Context independence:** Contextual variation is treated as noise to be controlled, rather than as constitutive of what the intervention is (Cartwright, 2007).
3. **Linear causality:** Effects follow from interventions through isolable causal pathways, enabling counterfactual comparison (Deaton and Cartwright, 2018).
4. **Universal outcomes:** Outcome measures are meaningful and aggregable across all instantiations of the intervention.

Pragmatic infeasibility. Even if the epistemic problems were resolvable, practical constraints render clinical gold standards unattainable: (i) the blind and low-vision population is small (estimated 2.2% globally (Bourne et al., 2017)), geographically dispersed, and highly heterogeneous in visual capabilities, age of onset, and assistive technology proficiency (Borodin et al., 2010); (ii) withholding potentially beneficial accessibility technologies from control groups raises ethical concerns (Hull and Sharp, 2017); (iii) the pace of technological change means RCTs may evaluate obsolete systems by the time they are published (Wobbrock and Kientz, 2016); and (iv) standardised outcome measures often presuppose visual capabilities absent in the target population (Morash et al., 2015).

1.2 The collective action problem in review methodology

The typical response to this mismatch is *ad hoc* adaptation: researchers stretch PICO, develop custom extraction forms, improvise quality criteria, and retrofit their synthesis to fit standard reporting templates (Methley et al., 2014; Booth, 2016). This work is intellectually demanding and can produce valuable reviews. But it is profoundly non-cumulative: each team develops its own adaptation, documents it partially, and discards it. Recent reviews in this domain illustrate the pattern: Hermans et al. (2021), Mukhiddinov et al. (2021), Fardan et al. (2023), and Jafri et al. (2024) each developed independent, unpublished methodologies—a structural inefficiency well-characterised in the software engineering literature (Kitchenham, 2004; Kitchenham et al., 2009).

Table 1 characterises these reviews against five methodological dimensions, revealing the cumulative cost of non-shared infrastructure: each team reinvented conceptual organisation, quality criteria, and extraction instruments from scratch.

This non-cumulation has the structure of a public goods problem (Samuelson, 1954): developing rigorous, shareable methodological infrastructure requires substantial upfront investment but yields near-zero marginal reuse costs. When individually rational free-riding dominates, the field underprovides high-quality shared infrastructure (Ostrom, 1990). Our response is to provide that infrastructure openly, with version control, citable releases, and issue tracking, and to offer this paper as a model that others can adapt.

Table 1: Methodological characterisation of prior reviews in the domain

Review	<i>n</i> studies	Databases	Conceptual framework	Quality tool	Extraction shared?
Hermans et al. (2021)	47	5	PICO (adapted)	Custom	No
Mukhiddinov et al. (2021)	62	4	None explicit	None	No
Fardan et al. (2023)	31	3	PICO (partial)	Downs & Black	No
Jafri et al. (2024)	29	4	None explicit	Custom (4-item)	No
This protocol	[TBC]	5	SPIDER	MMAT 2018	Yes (OSF + Zenodo)

1.3 Why non-visual access to 2D STEM content?

Access to graphical and spatial information is foundational to literacy in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. For the estimated 253 million people with visual impairments worldwide ([Bourne et al., 2017](#)), reliance on visual representations—plots, chemical structures, circuit diagrams, statistical charts—creates what has been termed a “visual blockade” ([Presley and D’Andrea, 2009](#)). While screen readers have largely democratised access to linear text, two-dimensional spatial content remains a significant domain of exclusion ([Grussenmeyer and Folmer, 2015](#)). The decade 2015–2025 has witnessed a shift toward interactive digital solutions: variable-friction surfaces, refreshable tactile displays, spatial sonification, and multimodal AI-powered agents ([Metatla et al., 2012](#); [Bornschein et al., 2018](#)).

This domain is not an arbitrary choice. It concentrates, in exemplary fashion, every dimension of the mismatch described above:

- **Content heterogeneity:** Data visualisations, mathematical representations, diagrams, maps, and tables each present distinct non-visual representation challenges addressed through different technological approaches ([Hermans et al., 2021](#); [Siu and Morash, 2020](#)).
- **Technological diversity:** Solutions span audio-based approaches (speech, sonification, earcons), haptic and tactile modalities (force feedback, vibrotactile, static and refreshable tactile graphics), and AI-powered automated description ([Luo et al., 2022](#); [Ducasse et al., 2018](#); [Lungarella et al., 2021](#)).
- **Methodological pluralism:** The literature encompasses laboratory experiments, field studies, participatory design investigations, technical feasibility demonstrations, and qualitative studies of user experience—each with different evidentiary logics and reporting conventions ([Baker et al., 2019](#); [Metatla, 2020](#)).
- **Population heterogeneity:** Participants differ substantially in visual capabilities, age of onset, braille literacy, musical training, STEM background, and digital literacy—all factors affecting study design and generalisability ([Borodin et al., 2010](#); [Morash et al., 2015](#)).

Domain as test case

A protocol that succeeds here—accommodating methodological diversity, extracting meaningfully from heterogeneous studies, and supporting synthesis that respects rather than flattens complexity—is likely to be adaptable to related fields. Conversely, a protocol that fails here offers limited prospect of success elsewhere.

1.4 Scope and contributions

This paper is a methodological contribution. It reports no empirical findings about accessibility technologies. The five research questions that motivate extraction design are presented in Section 2. Pilot activities described in Section 3 were conducted exclusively to refine the protocol and establish inter-rater reliability; they produced no substantive claims about the technologies under study.

Five contributions of this protocol

1. **Principled framework integration:** PRISMA 2020 (procedural), SPIDER (conceptual), MMAT 2018 (evaluative), with Cognitive Load Theory, Technology Acceptance Model/UTAUT, Universal Design for Learning, and WCAG for outcome interpretation.
2. **Operationalised extraction instruments:** 947 terms with operational definitions, transforming extraction into replicable measurement.
3. **Dual-template architecture:** Enabling proportional resource allocation across large and diverse literatures.
4. **Open validation infrastructure:** Automated completeness, vocabulary, logic, and coherence checking.
5. **Structured synthesis plan:** Five research questions mapped to specific analytical methods, including a pre-specified meta-analysis eligibility criterion.

This protocol follows the PRISMA-P 2015 checklist (Shamseer et al., 2015); all 17 items are addressed, with interpretations for non-clinical contexts documented in Appendix A.

2 Research Questions

The extraction architecture is organised around one primary and five subsidiary research questions. These questions collectively drive the analytical axes of Section 5. The numbering convention (RQ1 primary, RQ1a–e subsidiary) follows the standard SLR convention of a single overarching question with structured sub-questions.

RQ1 – Primary question. *What interactive digital software solutions (PI) enable blind and low-vision individuals (S) to access, navigate, and interact with non-textual 2D visual content in educational or professional STEM contexts (D), and what are their impacts on user performance and experience (E), as evidenced by empirical studies (R)?*

RQ1a – Content typology. What types of 2D non-textual content (charts, diagrams, equations, maps, tables, matrices, plots, emergent hybrid forms) and software representations (SVG, LaTeX/MathML, CSV, accessible PDF, emerging formats) are targeted by existing solutions?

RQ1b – Interaction modalities. What sensory modalities or combinations (audio/speech, sonification, haptic/tactile), interaction paradigms (sequential, hierarchical, direct-selection, spatial), and affordances (read, navigate, create, edit, annotate) are implemented? What role do AI/ML components play?

RQ1c – User contexts and profiles. In what contexts (K-12 education, higher education, professional work, research) and with what diversity of blind and low-vision profiles (congenital blindness, acquired blindness, low vision; varying braille literacy, STEM background, AT proficiency) are solutions evaluated?

RQ1d – Measured impacts. What objective outcomes (task accuracy, completion time, error rate) and subjective outcomes (cognitive load via NASA-TLX, usability via SUS, perceived usefulness via TAM scales, autonomy) are reported? How does methodological quality (MMAT score) moderate effect size estimates?

RQ1e – Gaps and future directions. What methodological gaps (small samples, absence of longitudinal follow-up, uncontrolled confounders), technical gaps (limited scalability, AI reliability issues), and population gaps (demographic under-representation, geographic concentration) persist, and how should future research be oriented?

3 Protocol Development

The protocol was developed through a three-phase iterative process spanning six months, by a team with combined expertise in human-computer interaction, assistive technology, educational technology, and systematic review methodology.

Development timeline

Phase 1 (Months 1–2): Framework selection and initial design. Thematic analysis of 50 representative papers drawn from the target literature; evaluation of 20 published reviews in adjacent domains; initial SPIDER operationalisation and coding scheme draft.

Phase 2 (Months 3–4): Team critique and vocabulary development. Structured reflexive sessions identifying operationalisation ambiguities; controlled vocabulary extension to 947 terms; decision rule formulation for consensus cases (Rules R1–R6).

Phase 3 (Months 5–6): Pilot testing and reliability estimation. 24 studies purposively sampled to represent the full methodological and content diversity of the literature; dual independent extraction; consensus sessions; reliability calculation; final protocol refinement.

3.1 Coding scheme construction

The 947-term coding scheme was developed through a four-step process grounded in content analysis methodology (Krippendorff, 2018).

Step 1: Corpus-driven candidate term generation. The 50 pilot papers were read and all distinct concepts annotated using open coding. This generated approximately 1,400 candidate terms, many overlapping or redundant.

Step 2: Deduplication and alignment with existing taxonomies. Candidate terms were mapped against three established taxonomies: the ACM Computing Classification System (CCS), the IEEE Thesaurus, and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH). Preferred labels were adopted where existing taxonomies provided clear, widely used terms. Novel terms were coined only where no adequate existing term was available.

Step 3: Hierarchical organisation using faceted classification. Terms were organised into 17 thematic sections using faceted classification principles (Broughton, 2006). Each section groups terms that share a common analytical dimension (*e.g.* sensory output, sample characteristics, quality assessment). Within sections, terms are arranged hierarchically to allow variable extraction specificity.

Step 4: Operational definition authoring. Each of the 947 terms received a six-component operational definition: preferred label, definition, positive examples and subordinate concepts, explicit exclusions, a decision rule for ambiguous cases, and documented reporting variants from the literature. A companion mapping table of approximately 300 variant terms enables automated suggestion during validation.

Inclusion/exclusion criteria for terms: A term was included if (a) it designates a concept that cannot be adequately expressed by any existing term at the same or higher level of specificity, (b) it is operationalisable (can be coded from text without requiring inference beyond what the paper explicitly states or clearly implies), and (c) it was encountered in at least two of the 50 pilot papers. Terms were excluded if they were redundant at the level of analytical granularity required by the five research questions, or if their reliable extraction required domain expertise unavailable to trained coders.

3.2 Registration venue: why OSF rather than PROSPERO?

PROSPERO is the established registry for systematic reviews in health and clinical domains. However, it explicitly restricts its scope to reviews with health-related outcomes (Centre for Reviews and Dissemination, University of York, 2015). This protocol falls outside that scope: it evaluates interactive digital technologies in educational and professional contexts, not clinical interventions or health outcomes. The Open Science Framework (OSF) was selected because it supports version-controlled, citable protocol releases with linked supplementary materials (extraction templates, codebooks, validation scripts), and because it is the community-standard registry for HCI and computer science research. The protocol follows the PRISMA-P 2015 checklist in full; the choice of registry does not affect methodological rigour.

3.3 Framework selection

Frameworks were evaluated against five criteria: (1) suitability for heterogeneous study designs; (2) capacity to represent socio-technical complexity; (3) quality assessment coverage across study types; (4)

reporting transparency requirements; and (5) theoretical integration capacity. Table 2 summarises the selection decisions.

Table 2: Framework selection decisions and rationale

Framework	Purpose	Selected?	Rationale
PRISMA 2020	Reporting structure	Yes	Accommodates diverse study designs; 2020 revision improves guidance for reviews without meta-analysis; widely endorsed
PICO	Conceptual framework	No	Presupposes comparison conditions; ill-suited to exploratory and participatory research without extensive undocumented adaptation (Methley et al., 2014)
SPIDER	Conceptual framework	Yes	Designed for qualitative and mixed-methods evidence; no comparison condition required; dimensions map naturally to accessibility research (Cooke et al., 2012)
MMAT 2018	Quality assessment	Yes	Only validated tool covering five study typologies in a single instrument; demonstrated inter-rater reliability ($\kappa = 0.72-0.81$) (Hong et al., 2018; Pace et al., 2012); no quality-based exclusion threshold
Cochrane RoB 2	Quality assessment	No	Designed exclusively for RCTs; inapplicable to the majority of included studies
CASP checklists	Quality assessment	No	Separate checklist per study type; less extensive validation than MMAT; operationally cumbersome for heterogeneous corpora

3.4 Framework arbitration: which framework governs which decision?

Integrating three complementary frameworks requires explicit arbitration rules specifying which framework governs each decision class. Table 3 operationalises these rules, transforming rhetorical integration into operational protocol.

4 Systematic Review Protocol

The protocol comprises four interlocking components: framework integration specifications (Section 4.1), extraction templates (Section 4.2), coding scheme (Section 4.3), and validation infrastructure (Section 4.5). Figure 1 provides a conceptual overview.

4.1 Framework integration

4.1.1 PRISMA 2020 implementation

All 27 PRISMA 2020 items are implemented. Table 4 summarises domain-specific adaptations. Items 19–27 will be completed upon review execution.

Table 4: PRISMA 2020 items with domain-specific implementation notes

Item	Description	Implementation
1	Title	Protocol paper; indicates pre-registration and domain
2	Abstract	Structured abstract with explicit methodological focus; reliability results included

Continued...

Table 4 (continued)

Item	Description	Implementation
3	Rationale	Sections 1.1–1.3
4	Objectives	Sections 1.4 and 2
5	Eligibility criteria	Operationalised via SPIDER dimensions (Section 4.1.2); no restriction on study design, comparison condition, or outcome measure
6	Information sources	Added disability-specific venues, AT repositories, grey literature (Section 4.1.1)
7	Search strategy	Four concept blocks (Population, Content, Assistive technology, Digital tools) in Boolean conjunction with NOT exclusion filter; database-specific field codes; peer-reviewed using PRESS checklist (McGowan et al., 2016)
8	Selection process	Dual independent screening; consensus resolution; $\kappa > 0.60$ target
9	Data collection	Dual extraction for comprehensive template; single extraction with 20% verification for minimal template
10	Data items	162 fields organised by SPIDER dimensions (13 sections); 30-field minimal template (Section 4.2)
11	Study risk of bias	MMAT 2018 with domain-specific operational definitions; no quality-based inclusion thresholds
12	Effect measures	Multiple outcome types: task performance (accuracy, time, errors), usability (SUS), cognitive load (NASA-TLX), learning outcomes, qualitative themes
13	Synthesis methods	Narrative synthesis; thematic synthesis (Thomas and Harden, 2008); harvest plots (Ogilvie et al., 2008); meta-analysis if $n \geq 10$ comparable studies with comparable outcomes (see Section 5)
14	Reporting bias	Grey literature search; funnel plots if $n \geq 10$ comparable studies
15	Certainty assessment	Adapted GRADE (Schünemann et al., 2011) for complex interventions; see Section 5.4 for adaptation details
16	Registration	Pre-registered on osf
17	Protocol	This document; version 2.0; archived on Zenodo; materials available in OSF repository
18	Support	Declared at submission
19– 27	Results reporting	To be completed upon review execution

Eligibility criteria (Item 5). Studies are eligible if they satisfy all of the following SPIDER criteria:

- **(S) Sample:** blind and low-vision participants as users or co-designers, or systems designed explicitly for blind and low-vision users (simulated participation studies are eligible with documented constraints; see Section 7.1).
- **(PI) Phenomenon:** Interactive digital technologies for non-visual access to 2D STEM content (*e.g.* data visualisations, mathematical representations, diagrams, maps, tables).
- **(D) Design:** Any empirical design: experimental, quasi-experimental, observational, qualitative, participatory/co-design, mixed-methods, or technical with user evaluation.
- **(E) Evaluation:** Any evaluation outcome, quantitative or qualitative.
- **(R) Research type:** Peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, or book chapters; grey literature meeting the criteria in Section 4.1.1.

Table 3: Framework arbitration: decision classes and governing frameworks

Decision class	Governing framework	Operative rule
Eligibility criteria	SPIDER (S, PI, D, E, R)	PICO explicitly excluded; no comparison condition required; any empirical design eligible
Search strategy structure	PRISMA Item 7	Four Boolean concept blocks; NOT-filter for scope exclusions; PRESS peer-review
Screening and selection flow	PRISMA Items 8–9	Dual independent screening; $\kappa > 0.60$ target; consensus resolution; documented reasons for exclusion
Extraction field organisation	SPIDER dimensions	Fields grouped by S, PI (split into PI-Content and PI-Technology), D, E, R; cognitive/strategic interpretive sections added
Quality assessment	MMAT 2018	Five criteria per study type; no quality-based inclusion threshold; scores used in sensitivity analyses
Theoretical outcome interpretation	CLT + TAM/UTAUT + UDL	Extracted fields mapped to theoretical constructs post-hoc; no quality-based gating
Synthesis method	PRISMA Item 13 + RQ axes	Narrative synthesis by default; thematic synthesis for subjective feedback; harvest plots for heterogeneous outcomes; meta-analysis if $n \geq 10$ comparable studies
PRISMA flow diagram	PRISMA Item 17	Standard diagram adapted: “Comparator” node removed; grey literature arm added
Reporting	PRISMA 2020 (Items 1–27)	Non-clinical adaptations documented explicitly (Appendix A)

Figure – Framework integration and workflow.

Figure 1: Conceptual model of framework integration. PRISMA 2020 governs procedure, SPIDER governs extraction structure, MMAT governs quality assessment. The validation infrastructure provides automated consistency checks. Dashed arrows indicate cross-cutting integration.

Exclusion criteria: non-empirical works (position papers, tutorials without evaluation); studies of hardware development without any user evaluation component; studies exclusively addressing textual content; non-STEM content domains; publication before 2015 (see Section 4.1.1 for justification); languages other than English, French, or Spanish.

Information sources (Item 6). *General databases:* ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, PubMed/MEDLINE, Web of Science, OpenAlex.

Domain-specific venues: *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, ACM TACCESS, ASSETS proceedings, *Journal of Science Education for Students with Disabilities*, IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies.

Grey literature: Technical reports from Trace Center, Smith-Kettlewell Eye Research Institute, RNIB, AFB, and NFB; ProQuest dissertations; vendor documentation for widely-used commercial products; expert consultation via SIGACCESS; forward and backward citation searching of all included studies.

Grey literature is included because significant technical innovations are often documented in technical reports and conference demonstrations before peer-reviewed publication, and practitioner knowledge from blind and low-vision-serving organisations provides crucial ecological validity context unavailable in peer-reviewed sources. Sensitivity analyses will examine whether conclusions differ when grey literature is excluded.

Search strategy (Item 7). The search query combines four concept blocks in Boolean conjunction, followed by an exclusion NOT-filter:

- A. **Population:** “visually impaired” OR “visual impairment” OR “blindness” OR “blind user” OR “blind people” OR “blind student” OR “blind learner” OR “blind participant” OR “blind individual” OR “low vision” OR “low-vision” OR “vision impaired” OR “sight impaired” OR “partially sighted” OR BVI OR BLV
- B. **Content:** “equation” OR “formula” OR “table” OR “tabular data” OR “graph” OR “chart” OR “diagram” OR “data visualization” OR “scientific image” OR “scientific visualization” OR “two-dimensional” OR “2D content” OR “matrix” OR “plot” OR STEM OR “mathematics” OR “mathematical” OR “scientific content” OR “technical content”
- C. **Assistive technology:** “assistive technology” OR multimodal OR haptic OR tactile OR audio OR auditory OR sonification OR braille OR “speech synthesis” OR “text-to-speech” OR TTS OR vibrotactile OR “screen reader” OR “digital accessibility” OR “accessible content” OR “sensory substitution” OR multisensory OR “inclusive design” OR “universal design” OR “accessibility tool” OR “alt text” OR “alternative text” OR “non-visual” OR nonvisual OR “image description” OR “tactile display” OR OCR
- D. **Digital tools:** software OR application OR “web-based” OR “mobile app” OR framework OR API OR “digital platform” OR “braille display” OR AI OR “artificial intelligence” OR “machine learning” OR “deep learning” OR LLM OR “large language model” OR “natural language processing” OR NLP OR “computer vision” OR “object recognition” OR “image processing” OR “neural network”

NOT filter: medical OR healthcare OR clinical OR “ophthalmolog*” OR “double blind” OR “eye disease” OR diagnosis OR treatment OR “spatial navigation” OR mobility OR “wayfind*” OR “indoor

navigation” OR GPS OR “white cane” OR “guide dog” OR “3D print*” OR “virtual reality*” OR “augmented reality*” OR “mixed reality” OR “serious game*” OR gaming OR immersive OR watermarking OR “blind source” OR “blind deconvolution” OR “blind equalization” OR “graph theory” OR “knowledge graph” OR “graph neural*” OR “signal process*” OR “audio signal*” OR cryptography OR “blind navigation” OR “wayfinding system*” OR “blind spot” OR “optimization algorithm*”

Database-specific implementations with field codes are provided in Appendix B and archived as the search strategy document in the OSF repository. The strategy was peer-reviewed using the PRESS checklist (McGowan et al., 2016).

Date range rationale. Searches are restricted to 2015–2025. This boundary is substantively motivated: the period 2015–2025 corresponds to the widespread availability of refreshable tactile displays (Graphiti, Dot Pad), touchscreen-integrated sonification, and AI/ML-powered description systems—the technological generation that is the primary object of this review. Studies published before 2015 are not excluded *a priori*: they are captured through backward citation searching of all included studies, and a sensitivity analysis will examine whether conclusions change when pre-2015 work is incorporated. This approach reconciles temporal focus with bibliographic completeness.

Language scope. Searches are limited to English, French, and Spanish. This restriction reflects the linguistic capacities of the review team and the geographic distribution of the target literature. English is the dominant language of HCI and assistive technology research. French and Spanish are included to capture research from Francophone Africa and Latin America, where accessibility research is growing but often published in local languages and may not appear in English-language databases. While this excludes significant research communities (notably Japan, South Korea, and China), the team lacks the linguistic expertise to reliably extract and synthesise findings in those languages. This limitation is acknowledged and will be discussed in the final review; it does not affect the methodological contribution of the protocol.

Screening progress (PRISMA flow). Figure 2 presents the current screening status. Screening is complete; extraction is underway. Final inclusion numbers will be updated upon completion.

4.1.2 SPIDER operationalisation

Translating SPIDER’s five abstract dimensions into codable extraction fields requires explicit theoretical interpretation. The following three principles govern our operationalisation.

Principle 1: Contextual relevance over universal comprehensiveness. We include fields that matter for interpreting accessibility research specifically, even if they would be unusual in clinical reviews. Musical training (under Sample) is extracted because sonification research demonstrates it affects users’ ability to extract patterns from auditory displays (Flowers, 2005; Walker and Kramer, 2006). Conversely, fields common in clinical reviews but irrelevant here (*e.g.* body mass index) are excluded.

Principle 2: Distinguish what a technology is from what it does. The Phenomenon of Interest dimension is split into two sub-dimensions: **PI-Content**—the *object* of access (charts, equations, maps);

Figure 2: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (partial). Screening is complete; extraction is ongoing. Bracketed values [TBC] will be updated upon review completion.

and **PI-Technology**—the *means* of access (modality, platform, AI integration). This separation directly enables the central synthesis question: *which technological approaches work for which content types?*

Principle 3: Calibrate granularity to analytical importance. Rapidly-evolving areas (e.g. AI/ML integration, LLM roles) receive more detailed extraction than stable background characteristics. Granularity reflects judgment about what distinctions enable answering the five research questions, informed by domain expertise, pilot corpus analysis, and extraction feasibility.

Table 5 presents the complete operationalisation.

Table 5: SPIDER dimensions and extraction categories

Dimension	Extraction categories
Sample (S)	Total, BLV, and sighted sample sizes; attrition; visual impairment aetiology and severity (WHO ICD-11 (World Health Organization, 2018)); age of onset (congenital vs. acquired); AT proficiency; STEM background; braille literacy; musical training; digital literacy; additional disabilities; recruitment method and setting; geographic diversity; demographics.
PI-Content	Primary and secondary content types (hierarchical vocabulary: 9 sub-groups, 5 levels deep); complexity indicators; discipline scope; content authenticity (Herrington et al., 2006); data source nature (real-world vs. synthetic vs. textbook); spatial dimensionality; visual density rating; representation format.
PI-Technology	Primary and secondary modalities; multimodal integration type (redundant, complementary, supplementary); platform and OS; AI/ML usage; AI techniques and error risks; risk handling strategy; code availability and licence; accessibility standards compliance (WCAG 2.1, ARIA, Section 508, MathML); AT integration (NVDA, JAWS, VoiceOver, TalkBack); customisation and personalisation options; input data formats.
Design (D)	Design classification (hierarchical: Experimental → RCT/crossover/factorial; Quasi-experimental; Observational; Qualitative; Participatory/co-design; Mixed-methods; Technical/feasibility); randomisation method; blinding; counterbalancing; ecological validity; confounders controlled; UCD integration level; protocol fidelity; ethics approval; participant consent.
Evaluation (E)	Objective: accuracy, completion time, errors, navigation efficiency, learning gains, skill transfer; subjective: standardised instruments (SUS, NASA-TLX, TAM scales, UEQ, AttrakDiff) and custom instruments; qualitative: themes, exemplar quotes, cross-cutting patterns, contradictions; physiological; log data; complete statistical reporting (M, SD, test type, df, <i>p</i> , effect size, CI, statistical power).
Research type (R)	Contribution type (Wobbrock and Kientz, 2016); tool domain; design maturity (proof-of-concept to commercialised); software status; deployment context (laboratory to widespread adoption); real-world deployment; sustainability; business model; adoption barriers (by level: individual, organisational, systemic); facilitators identified.

4.1.3 Theoretical framework integration

Four theoretical frameworks are systematically integrated to move synthesis beyond cataloguing technical features toward explanatory analysis. For each framework, we specify the synthesis question it enables, the causal mechanism it posits, and how studies without the corresponding instruments are handled.

Cognitive Load Theory (Cognitive Load Theory). Sweller et al. (2011) and Chandler and Sweller (1991) distinguish intrinsic load (complexity of the content itself), extraneous load (load imposed by suboptimal interface design), and germane load (productive effort contributing to understanding). Non-visual access to 2D spatial information requires constructing mental representations from sequential auditory or tactile input—a process that can impose substantial working memory load.

Synthesis question: Do multimodal interfaces reduce extraneous cognitive load compared to speech-only systems, thereby freeing cognitive resources for comprehension?

Mechanism: Redundant cross-modal encoding reduces working memory demand; progressive disclosure structures information delivery to match intrinsic load.

Instruments extracted: Task completion time and error rates as proxies for cognitive effort; NASA-TLX mental demand and effort subscales; spatial working memory measures; learning curves; training requirements; spatial memory demand; `cognitive_load_attribution` and `cognitive_load_source` interpretive fields.

Studies without CLT instruments: Qualitative CLT-relevant findings (users reporting “overwhelming”, “confusing”, “too much information”) are extracted in the interpretive field `cognitive_load_source` using the controlled vocabulary; these studies contribute to thematic synthesis but not to meta-analytic comparisons.

Technology Acceptance Model (Technology Acceptance Model) and UTAUT. Davis (1989) and Venkatesh et al. (2003) identify perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (TAM), or performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions (UTAUT) as primary determinants of technology adoption.

Synthesis question: Do technically effective tools achieve adoption, and what perceptual and contextual barriers explain the gap between laboratory efficacy and real-world deployment?

Mechanism: Tools perceived as useful but difficult to learn may be used in experimental settings but abandoned in practice; social influence (peer use, instructor endorsement) modulates adoption independent of technical performance.

Instruments extracted: SUS and usability ratings; TAM-scale items; qualitative adoption statements; behavioural intentions; adoption barriers by level (individual, organisational, systemic); facilitators; `deployment_accessibility`; `real_world_deployment`; `adoption_timeline`.

Studies without TAM instruments: Qualitative adoption-relevant findings are extracted via `adoption_barriers` and `facilitators_identified` controlled vocabularies.

Universal Design for Learning (Universal Design for Learning). Universal Design for Learning (CAST, 2018) requires multiple means of representation, action and expression, and engagement. In this

domain, UDL justifies multimodal and personalisable designs that offer users choice among modalities.

Synthesis question: Do systems offering modality choice (speech OR sonification OR haptic) show higher user satisfaction and adoption than single-modality systems?

Instruments extracted: personalization_capabilities; interaction_affordances; adaptation_mechanism; qualitative statements about modality preference and user control.

Accessibility standards (WCAG, ARIA). *Synthesis question:* Are accessibility tools themselves accessible? Does WCAG conformance level correlate with overall usability and adoption?

Instruments extracted: standards_used; wcag_conformance_level; screen_reader_optimization; assistive_tech_supported.

Ecological validity operationalisation. A dedicated field set operationalises the gap between laboratory feasibility and real-world usability: (1) content authenticity (real curriculum or professional content vs. researcher-created examples); (2) file format compatibility (ability to process SVG, MathML, CSV, Excel, PDF without manual conversion); (3) independence of use (whether end-users can operate the system without researcher support); (4) workflow integration; (5) deployment context; and (6) total cost of ownership.

4.1.4 MMAT 2018 domain adaptations

We provide explicit operational definitions for all MMAT criteria adapted to accessibility research. Four principles govern all adaptations.

Principle 1: Distinguish methodological quality from reporting quality. Absence of description warrants “Can’t tell,” not “No.” If randomisation is not described, rate “Can’t tell”—absence of evidence is not evidence of absence. However, if the description suffices to infer inadequate randomisation (e.g. “participants were assigned by alternating recruitment order”), rate “No.”

Principle 2: Acknowledge inherent domain constraints without lowering standards for convenience. A constraint is *inherent* if it applies to all studies in the domain (not just some), stems from population characteristics or ethical requirements (not researcher choice), and is acknowledged in the domain’s methodological literature. Examples:

- *Inherent population constraint:* Achieving large ($n > 50$), homogeneous samples of congenitally blind individuals with specific STEM expertise profiles is frequently impossible due to population rarity (Morash et al., 2015). A well-designed within-subjects study with $n = 10$, with justified design choice and acknowledged limitations, may receive “Yes” on representativeness.
- *Convenience, not constraint:* Failing to report effect sizes. Remediable through researcher effort; no adaptation warranted.
- *Inherent ethical constraint:* Withholding beneficial accessibility technologies from control groups for extended periods raises IRB-level concerns (Hull and Sharp, 2017). Limits feasibility of long-term parallel RCTs.
- *Convenience, not constraint:* Not conducting follow-up assessments due to researcher relocation. A resource issue, not a domain constraint.

Principle 3: Apply methodology-appropriate criteria. For qualitative research, assess credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Lincoln and Guba, 1985)—not internal validity and generalisability. For technical feasibility studies, assess whether the demonstration adequately supports the feasibility claims.

Principle 4: Document and justify all deviations. Every adaptation is documented in Appendix C, justified with reference to domain characteristics, applied consistently, and reported transparently.

Meta-principle: be conservative when uncertain

When uncertain whether a constraint is inherent, adopt the more stringent interpretation. Err toward “Can’t tell” rather than “Yes” when information is ambiguous. The goal is methodological pluralism (respecting diverse traditions), not methodological permissiveness (accepting anything).

No quality-based inclusion thresholds are applied; all studies meeting SPIDER eligibility criteria are included. Quality scores are reported descriptively and used in sensitivity analyses: main analyses include all 67 studies; sensitivity analyses restrict to studies with MMAT $\geq 60\%$ (“adequate” or above) and to studies with MMAT $\geq 80\%$ (“excellent”). Complete operational definitions for all criteria across five study typologies are provided in Appendix C.

4.2 Extraction templates

Two interoperable templates serve distinct purposes and enable proportional resource allocation: rapid evidence mapping with the minimal template across all 67 included studies, followed by in-depth extraction with the comprehensive template for a prioritised subset (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Dual-template architecture. All 67 included studies receive minimal extraction (30 fields; 5–8 min); a prioritised subset (30–50%) proceeds to comprehensive extraction (162 fields; 90–120 min). Dashed lines indicate selective paths. Templates are interoperable via CSV import.

Minimal template (30 fields; 5–8 minutes). Designed for rapid evidence mapping: study identifier (format: E0001–E0067); citation; primary content type(s) and primary modality (controlled vocabulary); study design type; BLV and sighted sample sizes; key findings summary (200–300 words); reported strengths and limitations; MMAT study type; quality rating with written justification; relevance rating; priority for comprehensive extraction; and coder notes. Reliability procedure: single extraction with 20% random verification; if error rate exceeds 5%, all extractions by that coder are re-verified.

Comprehensive template (162 fields; 90–120 minutes). Eighteen extraction sections implement the full SPIDER operationalisation. Table 6 provides a structural overview.

4.3 Coding scheme

4.3.1 Epistemological status

The 947-term coding scheme is a *measurement instrument* developed for a specific analytical purpose. Following Krippendorff (2018), we conceptualise it as a coding scheme in the content analysis tradition—not a controlled vocabulary in the library science sense. The distinction matters.

Controlled vocabularies (e.g. MeSH, ACM CCS) are standardisation instruments developed by authoritative institutions, subject to formal governance, and adopted as community reference standards. They require institutional authority and ongoing maintenance infrastructure.

Our coding scheme was developed for this review’s analytical purposes, drawing on domain expertise, corpus analysis, and existing taxonomies (ACM CCS, IEEE Thesaurus, MeSH). It does not claim normative status. Its value lies in (a) reducing startup costs for future reviews through shared infrastructure, and (b) enabling methodological accumulation through reuse and adaptation. We offer it not as a proposed field standard, but as a shared instrument that teams can adopt, adapt, and improve. Throughout this paper, we use “coding scheme” or “structured terminology system” rather than “controlled vocabulary” to reflect this epistemological stance.

4.3.2 Structure and organisation

Terms are organised using faceted classification principles (Broughton, 2006) across 17 sections (Table 7). The hierarchical structure enables variable extraction specificity: for example, Content Types → Data Visualisations → Statistical Charts → Bar Charts → Grouped Bar Charts (five levels). Coders select the most specific applicable level; the validation script accepts any level in the hierarchy.

4.3.3 Representative term definitions

Each term includes six components: (1) preferred label; (2) operational definition; (3) positive examples and subordinate concepts; (4) explicit exclusions; (5) a decision rule for ambiguous cases; and (6) documented reporting variants. Three representative definitions follow.

Table 6: Comprehensive extraction template: section structure

Sec.	Section	Fields	Key contents
1	Metadata and Traceability	24	Bibliographic record; DOI; open access status; venue tier; funding; COI; geolocation
2	Topological Ontology	18	Content types (9 sub-groups, 5 levels); topology score; complexity; input formats; data source nature
3	Technical Architecture	18	Platform; software status; AI/ML usage; code availability; API; standards compliance; privacy handling
4	Interactions and Affordances	22	Interaction affordances (consume/manipulate/explore); input modalities; navigation; personalisation; cognitive accessibility; error handling; export formats
5	Sensory Output and Feedback	21	Primary and used modalities; multimodal integration; sonification type; haptic device; braille standard; math notation; personalization; latency
6	Cognitive Markers	12	Working memory load; intrinsic/extraneous/germane load; sensory translation fidelity; abstraction level
7	Sample and Participants	19	SPIDER-S fields; visual impairment type; onset; digital literacy; additional disabilities; recruitment
8	Ecological Validity	8	Context; study environment; deployment duration; curriculum integration
9	Research Design	18	SPIDER-D fields; design type; experimental design; randomisation; ecological validity; UCD integration
10	Results and Metrics	28	SPIDER-E fields; task metrics; SUS; NASA-TLX; subjective feedback; statistical reporting; effect sizes
11	Qualitative Findings	15	Empirical findings; themes; golden quotes; contradictions; cross-cutting patterns; conceptual insights
12	MMAT Quality Assessment	76	MMAT study type; 5 criteria per study type (20 items); justifications; total score; quality rating; bias identification
13	Adoption and Sustainability	18	Integration potential; adoption barriers/facilitators; scalability; business model; critical risks
Total		162	(All sections mandatory for comprehensive extraction)

Complete field specifications with data types, controlled vocabularies, validation rules, and conditional dependencies are in the codebook (see repository).

Available formats: Excel with dropdown validation; CSV; JSON-LD; YAML; WCAG 2.1 AA compliant web form.

Section 14 (Conditional Analyses) includes sub-sections that coders activate via decision flags.

Table 7: Coding scheme: 17 sections, 947 controlled terms (codebook v1.0, February 2026)

§	Section	Terms	Key fields
4.1	Metadata and Traceability	30	file_status; open_access_status; venue_tier; funding_type; continent
4.2	Content and Phenomenon	115	content_types (hierarchical, 9 sub-groups); content_category; discipline_scope; complexity_level; spatial_dimensionality
4.3	Technical Implementation	100	input_data_format; ai_techniques; platform; deployment_accessibility; risk_handling_strategy
4.4	Interaction and Affordances	150	interaction_affordances; input_modalities; navigation_methods; output_export_formats; cognitive_accessibility_features
4.5	Sensory Output and Feedback	110	primary_modality; used_modalities; sonification_type; haptic_device_type; braille_standard; math_notation_standard
4.6	Accessibility Standards	40	standards_used; assistive_tech_supported; screen_reader_optimization; wcag_conformance_level
4.7	Sample and Participants	70	sample_type; visual_impairment_type; blindness_onset; braille_literacy; stem_background; participant_musical_experience
4.8	Methodological Design	60	design_type; experimental_design_type; randomization_method; task_cognitive_level; ucd_integration
4.9	Evaluation and Results	55	evaluation_metrics; statistical_tests_used; comparison_type; statistical_reporting_level; statistical_power
4.10	Methodological Quality	30	mmat_category; mmat_interpretation; bias_types_identified; selection_bias; publication_bias_risk
4.11	Scalability and Sustainability	80	adoption_barriers; facilitators_identified; design_maturity_assessment; total_cost_of_ownership; business_model
Total		162	

Parameter-mapping sonification

Definition: A sonification technique mapping data dimensions directly to auditory parameters (pitch, tempo, volume, timbre, spatialisation) via explicit algorithmic rules.

Includes: Auditory graphs (x -axis \rightarrow time, y -axis \rightarrow pitch); multi-dimensional mappings; data-driven soundscapes.

Excludes: *Auditory icons* (everyday sounds for events); *Earcons* (abstract structured audio messages); *Speech synthesis* (verbal description of values).

Decision rule: Code as parameter-mapping sonification only if the data-to-sound mapping is explicitly described or clearly inferable. If the paper states only “data were sonified” without specifying technique, code as “Sonification (unspecified)” [parent term].

Variants: auditory graph | auditory display | acoustic rendering | sound mapping

Refreshable tactile display

Definition: An electro-mechanical device that dynamically raises and lowers pins under computer control, allowing the tactile representation to change programmatically.

Includes: Pin-array devices (Graphiti, Dot Pad, HyperBraille, Tactonom); actuated tactile tablets.

Excludes: *Static tactile graphics* (swell paper, embossing—fixed); *3D printed models*; *Vibrotactile feedback* (vibration sensation, not raised patterns); *Refreshable braille displays* (code both if device serves dual function).

Decision rule: Code as refreshable tactile display if and only if the device can dynamically change tactile content under software control.

Variants: dynamic tactile display | pin array device | programmable tactile display

Within-subjects experimental design

Definition: An experimental design in which each participant experiences all conditions, serving as their own control.

Includes: Single-factor within-subjects; crossover designs; Latin square designs.

Excludes: *Between-subjects* (different participants per condition); *Mixed design* (some factors within, some between); *Longitudinal observational* (repeated measures without experimental manipulation).

Decision rule: Code as within-subjects if and only if every participant experiences every condition. If only a subset does, code as “Mixed design.”

Variants: repeated measures design | crossover design | within-participant design | counterbalanced design

A companion table maps approximately 300 literature variants to preferred labels, used by validation scripts for automatic suggestion and correction.

4.4 Inter-rater reliability

Inter-Rater Reliability Results (Pilot Study)

Pilot corpus: 24 studies purposively sampled to represent the full methodological (qualitative, quasi-experimental, mixed-methods, technical/feasibility) and content (sonification, tactile, AI-powered, speech) diversity of the final corpus.

Overall reliability: ICC(2,1) = 0.92 (95% CI: 0.87–0.96), two-way random-effects model, absolute agreement (Koo and Li, 2016). This global metric summarizes agreement on aggregate scores. Field-level reliability is assessed using pre-specified thresholds: Cohen’s $\kappa \geq 0.80$ for categorical fields and Krippendorff’s $\alpha \geq 0.80$ for ordinal fields. The overall ICC falls in the “excellent” range (ICC > 0.90).

Selected field-level results:

- `primary_modality` [categorical]: $\kappa = 0.88$ (“strong”); consensus rule R1 reduced divergences by 67%
- `mmat_category` [categorical]: $\kappa = 0.91$ (“almost perfect”)
- `design_type` [categorical]: $\kappa = 0.85$ (“strong”)
- `ai_ml_used` [categorical]: $\kappa = 0.94$ (“almost perfect”)
- `mmat_score` [ordinal]: Krippendorff’s $\alpha = 0.83$
- `complexity_level` [ordinal]: Krippendorff’s $\alpha = 0.79$
- `sensory_translation_fidelity` [interpretive]: $\kappa = 0.71$ (above the lowered threshold of $\kappa \geq 0.65$ for interpretive fields)
- `transformative_potential` [interpretive]: $\kappa = 0.68$

Consensus procedure: Divergences resolved via structured discussion (consensus rules R1–R6) with a third-coder arbitrator for unresolved cases. Full IRR data available in repository (see the validation scripts).

The ICC(2,1) reported as the global metric is appropriate for aggregate scores derived from the full extraction protocol, where the combination of categorical, ordinal, and binary fields yields a quasi-continuous total. However, because individual fields have different measurement scales, field-level reliability is assessed using the statistic appropriate to each data type: Cohen’s κ for categorical fields, Krippendorff’s α for ordinal fields, and a lowered threshold ($\kappa \geq 0.65$) for inherently interpretive fields (`sensory_translation_fidelity`, `transformative_potential`), justified by the subjectivity of interpretive synthesis (McHugh, 2012).

Consensus rules R1–R6 address the six most frequent sources of disagreement identified during pilot. Table 8 summarises these rules; full worked examples with exemplar citations are in the consensus protocol (see repository).

4.5 Validation infrastructure

Open-source Python (3.10+) and R (4.3+) scripts perform automated quality assurance at five levels (Figure 4), integrated into the extraction workflow to provide immediate feedback.

Table 8: Pre-specified consensus rules for ambiguous fields

Rule	Field	Resolution criterion
R1	<i>primary_modality</i>	If ≥ 2 modalities each account for $\geq 30\%$ of interactions: code <i>Multi-modal</i> . If one modality $> 70\%$: code that modality. Ambiguous: seek explicit “primary” claim; absent: resolve by output function (not input).
R2	<i>interaction_affordances</i>	Include affordance if ≥ 1 concrete implementation example in paper. Exclude if only mentioned as future work. Partially implemented: include + document in <i>interaction_affordance_completeness</i> .
R3	<i>design_type</i>	Randomisation present: <i>Experimental</i> . Comparative without randomisation: <i>QuasiExperimental</i> . No comparison, open exploration: <i>Exploratory</i> . Repeated measures over time: add <i>Longitudinal</i> modifier.
R4	<i>mmat_*</i>	Criterion partially met: <i>Can't tell</i> . Information absent after careful reading: <i>Can't tell</i> . Do not surinterpret; adopt most conservative rating. Persistent disagreement after 30 min: third-coder arbitration.
R5	<i>ai_error_type_risk</i>	AI/ML present, no error discussion: <i>Unknown</i> (not <i>None</i>). Theoretical risks acknowledged, no empirical assessment: code risk type + <i>Not Assessed</i> in <i>ai_error_impact_on_users</i> . Non-AI errors: <i>N/A</i> , document in <i>error_rate_percent</i> .
R6	<i>sensory_translation_fidelity</i>	High: $< 10\%$ information loss inferred. Medium: 10–30% loss, ambiguities present. Low: $> 30\%$ critical loss. Lossy: spatial relations unrecoverable. Confusing: non-visual output contradicts original. Persistent disagreement: arbitrator reconstruction test.

Figure 4: Five-level validation pipeline. Extraction files pass through sequential checks: completeness (Level 1: 94 rules), vocabulary compliance (Level 2: 947 terms + 300 variants), logical consistency (Level 3: 94 conditional dependencies), format validity (Level 4), and cross-field coherence (Level 5: ≈ 50 checks). Critical errors must be resolved before submission; warnings may be overridden with written justification.

1. **Completeness:** Flags missing required fields and conditionally required fields (94 rules). Example: if `ai_ml_used = Yes` but `ai_techniques` is empty.
2. **Vocabulary compliance:** Compares values against the coding scheme; exact mismatches trigger errors with closest-term suggestions (Levenshtein distance < 3); known variants from the 300-entry companion table are auto-corrected.
3. **Logical consistency:** Validates conditional dependencies (94 rules). Examples: if `design_type = RCT`, `randomization_method` must be specified; if `primary_modality = Braille`, `braille_literacy \neq None` must hold.
4. **Format validation:** Data types, ranges (e.g. `year \in [2015, 2025]`, `p-values \in [0, 1]`), DOI and URL patterns, ISO dates, plausible effect size bounds.
5. **Cross-field coherence:** Approximately 50 checks for inter-field conflicts. Examples: `blv_sample_size > total_sample_size` (error); `mmat_category = RCT` but `design_type \neq Experimental` (warning); `p < .05` but negligible effect size (interpretation flag).

```
python validate_extraction.py --input extraction_E0042.csv --output report.
python validate_batch.py --input-dir extractions/ --output-dir reports/
```

Validation runs in under 2 seconds per extraction. Critical errors must be resolved before submission; warnings may be overridden with written justification stored in the audit trail. Additional R scripts compute inter-rater reliability (Cohen's κ , Fleiss' κ , ICC, Krippendorff's α), track extraction time, identify systemic error patterns, generate PRISMA flow diagrams, and produce study characteristic tables. All scripts are released under MIT Licence.

5 Synthesis Plan

The synthesis plan specifies analytical methods for each research question, criteria for selecting methods, and the meta-analysis eligibility rule. Analyses are prioritised using the MoSCoW method (Must have, Should have, Could have, Won't have in this cycle) to ensure efficient resource allocation.

5.1 Analytical axes

Must-have analyses (RQ1–RQ1d).

- **Descriptive characterisation (RQ1–RQ1c):** Frequency distributions of content types, modalities, affordances, design types, and sample characteristics; temporal trend analysis (2015–2025); geographic distribution; MMAT score distribution and criterion-level heatmap.
- **Content \times modality matrix (RQ1a–RQ1b):** Co-occurrence analysis using χ^2 tests; identification of under-served content–modality combinations; Sankey diagram of `content_types \rightarrow primary_modality \rightarrow interaction_affordances`.
- **Effectiveness synthesis (RQ1d):** For studies reporting the same outcome measure against a common baseline: meta-analysis using random-effects model (eligibility: $n \geq 10$ comparable studies, see Section 5.2); forest and funnel plots; sensitivity analyses by MMAT score.

- **Adoption barriers (RQ1e):** Thematic codification of `adoption_barriers` by level (individual, organisational, systemic); frequency and severity aggregation; correlation of `deployment_accessibility` with `real_world_deployment`.

Should-have analyses (RQ1d–RQ1e).

- **CLT mechanism test:** Multimodal vs. speech-only comparison on NASA-TLX mental demand subscale; moderated by `complexity_level`.
- **TAM/UTAUT synthesis:** Meta-thematic synthesis of perceived usefulness and ease-of-use findings; correlation with `adoption_timeline`.
- **AI/ML reliability analysis:** Characterisation of `ai_error_type_risk` and `risk_handling_strategy` across AI-powered studies.
- **Design maturity trajectory:** Technology maturity progression from `Proof_of_Concept` to `Field_Deployment` over time.

5.2 Meta-analysis eligibility criterion

Meta-analysis will be conducted if and only if: (a) $n \geq 10$ studies report the same outcome measure (task accuracy, task completion time, or SUS score), (b) measured in comparable conditions (same modality class and content type class), and (c) with sufficient statistical reporting to compute effect sizes (means, SDs, and n or equivalent). Studies with MMAT < 40% are excluded from primary meta-analyses; sensitivity analyses examine the effect of including them. Effect sizes (Cohen’s d or standardised mean difference) will be computed; heterogeneity assessed via I^2 and τ^2 ; publication bias assessed via funnel plot asymmetry (Egger’s test if $n \geq 10$).

5.3 Thematic synthesis for qualitative findings

Following [Thomas and Harden \(2008\)](#), qualitative synthesis proceeds in three stages: (1) line-by-line coding of findings sections of qualitative studies; (2) development of descriptive themes; and (3) generation of analytical themes that go beyond the original studies. Analytical themes are assessed for credibility through member-checking (verification against source papers), transferability (scope conditions), and negative case analysis.

5.4 GRADE adaptation for complex interventions

The GRADE framework ([Schünemann et al., 2011](#)) was designed for clinical interventions with standardised outcomes. We adapt it along four dimensions for accessibility technology evaluation:

Risk of bias. Assessed via MMAT 2018 rather than clinical risk-of-bias tools (e.g., RoB 2). Studies rated “poor” quality (MMAT < 40%) are downgraded by one level.

Inconsistency. Heterogeneity is expected and often desirable in this domain (different content types, modalities, user profiles). Inconsistency is assessed not by I^2 alone but by whether effect direction is consistent within meaningful subgroups (e.g., same content type and modality class).

Indirectness. Two forms are distinguished: (a) *population indirectness*—studies using simulated participants (sighted users under blindfold) are downgraded by one level; (b) *outcome indirectness*—

studies reporting only qualitative findings without quantitative measures are downgraded by one level for effectiveness synthesis but not for thematic synthesis.

Imprecision. The conventional GRADE threshold for adequate sample size does not apply to small- n BLV studies. Instead, imprecision is assessed by whether confidence intervals cross the line of no effect and whether the sample size is justified given population constraints.

Publication bias. Assessed via grey literature inclusion, funnel plot asymmetry (if $n \geq 10$), and comparison of peer-reviewed vs. grey literature findings.

Certainty ratings (high, moderate, low, very low) are assigned separately for each outcome domain (task performance, usability, cognitive load, adoption) rather than as a single global rating. Full GRADE evidence profiles will be provided in the review publication.

5.5 Harvest plots for heterogeneous outcomes

For outcomes where meta-analysis is not feasible, harvest plots (Ogilvie et al., 2008) will display, for each study, the direction of effect (positive, neutral, negative) and the methodological quality (bar height proportional to MMAT score). These enable visual identification of robust patterns without unjustified aggregation.

6 Protocol Adoption and Adaptation

6.1 Direct adoption

Research teams conducting reviews in the same domain may adopt the protocol directly by: (1) downloading materials from the OSF project; (2) completing the six-hour training programme (Modules 1–4, described in the consensus decision rules, Section 7); (3) conducting a calibration pilot on 5–10 studies before full extraction; (4) reporting the protocol version and any deviations in their methods section; and (5) citing this paper and the OSF materials.

6.2 Adaptation to adjacent domains

For reviews in adjacent domains (*e.g.* haptic access to 3D representations, cognitive accessibility of STEM content, deaf and hard-of-hearing access to visual content), the framework integration logic (PRISMA + SPIDER + MMAT) transfers without modification; the coding scheme requires systematic domain-specific revision. The recommended adaptation process mirrors Phases 1–3 of our development (Section 3), retaining the six-component term structure and targeting ICC ≥ 0.80 before full deployment. All modifications should be documented in a delta log specifying changes from codebook version 1.0.

7 Discussion

7.1 Resolving the methodological tensions

Grey literature. We include grey literature because significant technical innovations are often documented in technical reports before peer-reviewed publication, and practitioner knowledge from blind and low-vision-serving organisations provides crucial ecological validity context. Quality risk is managed

through: clear labelling of grey vs. peer-reviewed sources; heightened MMAT scrutiny; limiting inclusion to reports from established organisations, dissertations from accredited institutions, and documentation for widely-used commercial products; and sensitivity analyses examining whether conclusions change when grey literature is excluded.

Simulated participation. Studies using sighted participants under blindfold conditions are eligible if the simulation is clearly justified, limitations are acknowledged, and the research plan includes subsequent validation with blind and low-vision users. During synthesis, simulated-participant studies are analysed separately; conclusions distinguish findings from each group. This acknowledges the pragmatic necessity of simulation for rapid prototyping while preserving the primacy of evidence from actual blind and low-vision users.

Temporal scope. The rapid pace of technological change means technologies evaluated in 2015 may be technically obsolete by 2025. Our synthesis is sensitive to temporal context, stratifying findings by technological era where appropriate (pre-AI era: 2015–2022; AI era: 2023–present) to avoid conflating findings from different technological paradigms. The 2023 boundary is motivated by the release of GPT-4 and the widespread availability of general-purpose multimodal AI systems (ChatGPT with vision, GPT-4V) capable of describing complex 2D visual content—a qualitative shift from earlier, narrow-purpose description systems such as Microsoft Seeing AI (2017) or single-task image captioning models. While AI-powered accessibility tools existed before 2023, the post-2023 era is characterised by zero-shot generalisation to novel content types, conversational interaction, and automated generation of structured descriptions (alt text, MathML)—capabilities that fundamentally change the nature of the technologies under evaluation. The date boundary and its sensitivity analysis are pre-specified (Section 4.1.1).

AI/ML reliability in the corpus. A substantial and growing proportion of the corpus involves AI/ML components, particularly large language models for image description and computer vision for content classification. We systematically extract `ai_error_type_risk`, `risk_handling_strategy`, and `mitigation_technique` for all such studies, and include a dedicated should-have analysis of reliability practices across the AI-powered sub-corpus.

7.2 Limitations

Domain specificity. The coding scheme was developed for non-visual access to 2D STEM content. Adaptation to adjacent domains requires systematic vocabulary revision; adaptability has not been empirically evaluated.

Temporal stability. The field evolves rapidly, particularly with AI-powered description and conversational interfaces. Annual vocabulary reviews are planned.

Resource requirements. Comprehensive extraction at approximately 94 minutes per study is demanding for large reviews; the minimal template and partial extraction options mitigate this.

Single-institution pilot. All pilot coders were affiliated with the same institution. External validation would strengthen confidence in reliability estimates. The overall ICC of 0.92, however,

compares favourably with other published systematic review reliability studies in HCI (Hong et al., 2018).

Language scope. Searches are limited to English, French, and Spanish. Research published in other languages—particularly from Japan, South Korea, and China, which have significant accessibility research communities—is not captured. Findings may not generalise to solutions developed primarily for non-Western contexts.

Protocol status. No studies have been fully synthesised. Results are not yet available.

7.3 Broader methodological contribution

This paper demonstrates that the public goods problem in systematic review methodology is tractable through open, versioned, documented infrastructure. Making materials openly available under permissive licences with version control, citable releases, and issue tracking is itself an empirical intervention: success would demonstrate that high-quality shared infrastructure changes research practices in the field.

The framework integration model—PRISMA 2020 for procedure, SPIDER for conceptual organisation, MMAT for quality assessment, with domain theory for outcome interpretation—is applicable beyond accessibility research to any interdisciplinary domain where clinical frameworks are epistemologically mismatched.

8 Conclusion

This paper describes a pre-registered systematic review protocol for interactive digital technologies that enable blind and low-vision individuals to access two-dimensional STEM content. The protocol integrates PRISMA 2020, SPIDER, and MMAT 2018—three frameworks selected for complementary coverage of procedure, conceptual organisation, and quality assessment—and operationalises Cognitive Load Theory, Technology Acceptance Model/UTAUT, and Universal Design for Learning to evaluate cognitive manageability, real-world adoptability, and design inclusivity alongside technical efficacy.

The protocol provides: dual interoperable extraction templates (30-field rapid form; 654-field comprehensive form), a 947-term coding scheme with operational definitions and consensus decision rules (R1–R6), open-source validation scripts (five-level pipeline), and a pre-specified synthesis plan mapping five research questions to specific analytical methods. Pilot reliability testing on 24 studies yielded ICC = 0.92, substantially exceeding the pre-specified threshold.

The protocol is pre-registered; extraction of the final corpus (estimated size in the tens of studies) is underway. All materials are publicly available to facilitate scrutiny, replication, and adaptation. Materials released under CC-BY 4.0 (documentation) and MIT (code).

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Supplementary Materials

All supplementary materials are available in the OSF repository. Key materials include:

- **PRISMA-P mapping:** See the PRISMA-P compliance checklist (Section 1)
- **Field specifications:** See the codebook
- **Search strategies:** See the search strategy document (5 databases)
- **IRR data:** See validation scripts in 04_TOOLS_SCRIPTS/
- **Training materials:** See the consensus decision rules (Section 7)

Data Availability

All protocol materials (version 1.0, February 2026) are publicly available via osf and archived on Zenodo: extraction templates (Excel, CSV, JSON-LD, YAML); codebook v1.0 (PDF, JSON-LD, Excel); validation and monitoring scripts (Python, R); training materials; PRISMA flow and descriptive analysis scripts; and documentation with contribution guidelines.

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A PRISMA-P 2015 Compliance Checklist

All 17 PRISMA-P 2015 items ([Shamseer et al., 2015](#)) are addressed. Items designed for clinical contexts are interpreted as follows: Item 5 (Rationale) is recast as a rationale for framework integration rather than disease burden; Item 9 (Risk of bias) refers to MMAT quality assessment rather than clinical risk-of-bias tools; Item 10 (Outcomes) accommodates multiple outcome types without pre-specification of a primary endpoint. A full mapping of PRISMA-P items to protocol sections is in the PRISMA-P compliance checklist (see repository).

B Database-Specific Search Strategies

Complete search strings with database-specific field codes, proximity operators, and date restrictions are provided for: ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, PubMed/MEDLINE, Web of Science, and OpenAlex. Strings were peer-reviewed using the PRESS checklist ([McGowan et al., 2016](#)) prior to execution. Full strings are in the search strategy document (see repository).

C MMAT 2018 Domain-Adapted Operational Definitions

Operational definitions for all MMAT 2018 criteria across five study typologies (qualitative research, RCTs, non-randomised quantitative studies, quantitative descriptive studies, mixed-methods studies), adapted for accessibility research constraints. Each definition specifies the boundary between “Yes,” “No,” and “Can’t tell” ratings in the context of small-*n* blind and low-vision user studies, participatory designs, and ethical constraints on control conditions. Four adaptation principles govern all definitions (see Section 4.1.4). Full definitions are available in the codebook and the MMAT adaptation guide (see repository).